

ISic1494

I.Sicily inscription 1494

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

cippus (?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Chiesa della Cattolica

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3565

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI313672

1. ²vestigia litterarum²
2. ιϰη' ϰ
3. Ἴοϰ ὕλι (οϰ) ϰ Ἴοϰσ (τοϰ)
4. συνβίο εϰ-
5. σεβεβέϰ ²⁶εϰσεβεβέϰ²⁶ ϰ
6. [— — — —]
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 40
Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 254 no.3

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